

Factors Associated with Therapeutic Non-Adherence in Type 2 Diabetes Patients at the Maradi Reference Hospital

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Abstract

Introduction. Type 2 diabetes (T2D) represents a major public health problem. Monitoring and control are hampered by the issue of non-adherence to treatment. The objective of this study was to identify the factors associated with non-adherence to treatment in patients with type 2 diabetes. **Methodology.** This was a descriptive, cross-sectional study of outpatients with type 2 diabetes. Sociodemographic variables, variables related to treatment adherence, and factors that could influence it were collected and analyzed. Adherence was assessed using the Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS). The results were analyzed using SPSS version 27.0.1. The dependent variable to be explained was non-adherence to treatment. For all statistical tests, the significance level (p-value) was set at 0.05. **Results.** The mean age was 51.09 years, with a range from 14 to 74 years. The 30-60 age group was the most represented, at 70.4%. The study population was predominantly female (63.9%), with a sex ratio of 0.56. Almost all patients were married, and 77.6% lived in urban areas. Secondary

More Information

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and higher education levels were the most represented, at 38% each. 55.6% of patients reported receiving family support. At the end of our study, we recorded 32.4% of patients with good adherence, 38.9% with moderate adherence, and 28.7% with non-adherence, giving us a prevalence of non-adherence (moderate adherence and non-adherence) of 67.6%. Family support and physical activity were significantly associated with poor compliance; however, neither smoking nor alcohol consumption, nor the use of traditional treatments, nor self-monitoring of blood glucose showed a statistically significant link with non-adherence to treatment. **Conclusion.** Therapeutic non-adherence is a problem affecting a large proportion of our included patients. The factors found to be significantly associated with poor compliance were family support and physical activity.

Introduction

Type 2 diabetes is a chronic metabolic disease that today constitutes a major global public health challenge, with serious complications when poorly controlled [1].

According to the IDF in 2024, an estimated 588.7 million adults were living with diabetes. The distribution by region shows strong heterogeneity: Europe had 453 million cases, North America and the Caribbean 56.2 million, Central and South America 35.4 million, and Southeast Asia 106.9 million. In sub-Saharan Africa, 24.6 million people had diabetes, while North Africa and the Middle East accounted for 84.7 million [2]. In Niger, the number of people living with diabetes was estimated at 505,900 in 2024 and could reach 1.6 million by 2050 [3].

To prevent its complications and ensure successful management of T2D, good therapeutic adherence must be guaranteed. However, like other chronic diseases, the follow-up and control of diabetes is faced with the problem of therapeutic non-adherence. According to the WHO, 50% of patients with a chronic disease do not take their treatment correctly [5]. The WHO concludes that: "improving a patient's adherence to a chronic treatment should prove as beneficial as any biomedical discovery" (2).

Therapeutic adherence can be defined as the degree of conformity between a patient's behavior and their doctor's recommendations [4]. Non-adherence is therefore a frequent phenomenon influenced by several factors: socio-demographic, economic, factors related to the disease and treatment, to the patient themselves, etc.

Several studies have been conducted in the capital, including that of MOUSSA Seydou in 2023 which focused on "factors associated with therapeutic non-

adherence in patients admitted for ketoacidosis at the National Hospital of Niamey". However, no study on the therapeutic adherence of diabetic patients has been conducted in the Maradi region.

The aim of the study is to fill this gap by providing specific data adapted to the local context to improve patient management.

Results

We recorded 108 patients meeting our inclusion criteria during the study period.

Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Patients

The mean age was 51.09 years with extremes ranging from 14 to 74 years. The 30 to 60-year-old age group was the most represented at 70.4%. The study population was predominantly female in 63.9% of cases, with a sex ratio of 0.56. Almost all patients were married and lived in urban areas in 77.6% of cases.

Secondary and higher education levels were the most represented at 38% each. 55.6% of patients reported receiving family support.

Adherence

At the end of our study, we recorded 32.4% of patients who showed good adherence, 38.9% of these patients were moderately adherent, and 28.7% were non-adherent, giving us a prevalence of non-adherence (moderately adherent and non-adherent) of 67.6%.

Table 1: Distribution of Patients According to Adherent and Non-Adherent Status

	Number	Percentage (%)
Adherent	35	32.4
Non-adherent	73	67.6
Total	108	100

Factors Associated with Adherence

Table 2: Socioeconomic and Demographic Factors and Their Link with Non-Adherence

Factors	Adherent (%)	Non-adherent (%)	P value
Age			0.118
<30 years	2 (5.7%)	3 (4.1%)	
30-60 years	21 (60%)	55 (75.3%)	
>60 years	12 (34.3%)	15 (20.5%)	
Gender			0.877
Male	13 (37.1%)	26 (35.6%)	
Female	22 (62.9%)	47 (64.4%)	

Marital status			0.487
Married	35 (100%)	72 (98.6%)	
Single	0 (0%)	1 (1.4%)	
Residence			0.546
Urban	26 (27.2%)	58 (56.8%)	
Rural	9 (25.7%)	15 (20.5%)	
Education level			0.333
No schooling	9 (25.7%)	9 (12.3%)	
Primary	3 (8.6%)	5 (6.8%)	
Secondary	11 (31.4%)	30 (41.1%)	
Higher	12 (34.3%)	29 (39.7%)	
Coverage (consultation)			0.234
Insured	22 (62.9%)	37 (50.7%)	
Uninsured	13 (37.1%)	36 (49.3%)	
Coverage (medication)			0.537
Insured	9 (25.7%)	23 (31.5%)	
Uninsured	26 (74.3%)	50 (68.5%)	
Family support			0.008
Yes	13 (37.1%)	47 (64.4%)	
No	22 (62.9%)	26 (35.6%)	

Table 3: Non-Adherence and Factors Related to the Health System

Factors	Adherent(%)	Non-adherent(%)	P value
Easy access to medication			0.438
Yes	21 (60%)	38 (52.1%)	
No	14 (40%)	35 (47.9%)	
Caregiver-patient relationship			-
Trust	35 (100%)	73 (100%)	
Distrust	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	
Appointment frequency			0.086
Once every two weeks	6 (17.1%)	12 (16.4%)	
Once a month	19 (54.3%)	33 (45.2%)	
Once every 2 months	0 (0.0%)	12 (16.4%)	
Once every 3 months	10 (28.6%)	16 (21.9%)	

The analysis of factors related to the health system shows that neither easy access to medication nor appointment frequency were significantly associated with therapeutic non-adherence. Furthermore, the

caregiver-patient relationship could not be evaluated statistically, as all interviewed patients declared having a relationship of trust with their care providers.

Table 4: Distribution of Patients According to the Factor Related to anti-Diabetics and Its Link with Non-Adherence

Type of treatment	Adherent (%)	Non-adherent (%)	P value
OAD (Oral Anti-Diabetic)	21 (60%)	51 (69.9%)	0.548
Insulin	11 (31.4%)	16 (21.9%)	
OAD+Insulin	3 (8.6%)	6 (8.2%)	

The type of treatment does not influence therapeutic non-adherence.

Table 5: Factors Related to the Disease and Their Link with Non-Adherence

Factors	Adherent (%)	Non-adherent (%)	P value
Duration of disease evolution			0.578
<1 year	10 (28.6%)	13 (17.8%)	
1 to 5 years	10 (28.6%)	20 (27.4%)	

6 to 10 years	5 (14.2%)	14 (19.2%)	
>10 years	10 (28)	26 (35.6%)	
Glycaemic control HbA1c:			0.969
Less than or equal to 7	7 (22.6%)	14 (22.2%)	
Greater than 7	24 (77.4%)	49 (77.8%)	
Comorbidity:			0.453
Yes	19 (54.3%)	34 (46.6%)	
No	16 (45.7%)	39 (53.4%)	

The duration of diabetes evolution as well as the presence of a comorbidity did not show a notable impact on non-adherence. Among the 108 patients included in the study, 93 had a recent glycated haemoglobin result, and no statistically significant association was found between glycaemic control and therapeutic non-adherence.

Physical activity is significantly associated with poor adherence; however, neither smoking, alcohol consumption, the use of traditional treatments, nor self-monitoring of blood glucose showed a statistically significant link with non-adherence to treatment.

Discussion

Socio-demographic and economic characteristics

The mean age of the study population was 51.09 years with extremes of 14 and 74 years. The 30-60-year-old age group was the most represented in 72.2% of cases in our series. This rate was close to that of Sangala in Mali in 2020 [51] who found 60.3% in the 40-60 age group; we note a significant concentration of participants in the adult age group because type 2 diabetes is primarily diagnosed in adulthood, a period marked by increased exposure to risk factors.

In our series, females were the most represented in 63.9% of cases (sex ratio 0.56), data which are close to those of Tchamdja in Togo in 2020 who found 62.5% women and a sex ratio of 0.6 [52]. This could be explained by the sample size and also the inclusion criteria, which included type 1 diabetes.

Secondary and higher education levels were the most represented at 38% each, which is higher than the data reported by Ezechiel [46] who found 21.54% respectively. This difference could be explained by a demographic disparity, notably the fact that our sample is mainly composed of patients from an urban environment where education levels are generally higher.

Prevalence of therapeutic adherence

This study on the prevalence of non-adherence to antihyperglycaemic agents in T2D cases showed that a large part of the patients were non-adherent. Indeed, we recorded 32.4% of patients who showed good adherence, 38.9% of moderately adherent patients, and 28.7% of non-adherent patients, giving us a prevalence of non-adherence (moderately adherent and non-adherent) of 67.6%. These results are close to those of Fatima Zahra [44] in 2016 in Algeria who found

33.7% adherent patients, 36.9% moderately adherent, and 29.4% non-adherent with a non-adherence prevalence of 66.3% and Tawfik [45] in 2013 in Egypt who found a non-adherence prevalence of 70%.

Factors influencing therapeutic non-adherence in type 2 diabetic patients

- **Factors related to socio-demographic and economic characteristics**

In this section, the only factor found to influence therapeutic non-adherence is family support (P= 0.008), which aligns with the results of Tawfik [45] and also Tiv in France in 2010 [55]. This is because support from loved ones can have a dual effect: it promotes therapeutic adherence when it is benevolent and adapted but can become a source of stress if it does not take into account the patient's real needs.[56].

The analysis of other variables, namely: age, gender, marital status, education level, coverage for consultation and medication did not show a statistically significant link with adherence. However, other authors have found a significant link between gender and non-adherence, such as Moussa Seydou in 2023 in Niger [50]. This could be explained by the sample size and also the inclusion criteria, which included type 1 diabetes. Also, Ezechiel [46] highlighted a statistically significant link between coverage (consultation) and non-adherence.

- **Factors related to anti-diabetics**

The type of treatment is not a factor influencing therapeutic non-adherence both in our study and in those of Badr [57] and Lansiné [47]. Generally, OADs are easier to take with less psychological impact [58].

- **Factors related to the disease**

The variables analysed here, namely the duration of disease evolution, glycaemic control (HbA1c), and the presence or absence of comorbidities, did not reveal a statistically significant link with non-adherence. The same observations were made by Fatima zahra [44] in Algeria in 2016, and Lamiaa in Morocco in 2012 [59]. However, Moussa Seydou [50] in Niger in 2023 noted a significant link between the duration of diabetes evolution and therapeutic non-adherence; this difference could be explained by the type of population studied: in our case, it involved outpatients, while the other study focused on patients hospitalised for ketoacidosis.

• Factors related to the health system

In our study, neither medication availability nor appointment frequency had an influence on non-adherence. The same observation was made by Bagonza [54]. This may be due to the fact that patients who reported encountering supply difficulties had not necessarily interrupted or abandoned their treatment. The caregiver-patient relationship in diabetic patients can modify therapeutic adherence because a good relationship could improve it, but a conflictual or distant relationship can have the opposite effect. In our study, the caregiver-patient relationship is optimal as all patients affirmed having a good relationship with their doctors.

Conclusion

Non-adherence to treatment among patients with type 2 diabetes is a major public health problem, particularly in resource-limited settings such as ours. This study identified family support and physical activity as factors associated with non-adherence. Strengthening patient education and improving access to care and medication are essential for improving treatment adherence among type 2 diabetic patients treated at the Maradi Reference Hospital.

Conflict of interest

None.

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